

The Phenylthiocarbamides. A Contribution to the Study of the Triad -N-C-S-. Part I. Aniline Thiocyanate.

BY HANS KRALL AND RAMESHWAR DAYAL GUPTA.

Hofmann (*Compt. rend.*, 1858, **47**, 424) first prepared phenylthiocarbamide by the union of ammonia and phenyl mustard oil and called it 'thiosinamine de la série phénylique'. Schiff (*Annalen*, 1868, **148**, 338) prepared it by heating aniline and ammonium thiocyanate under reflux, presumably in aqueous solution, but published no details.

Clermont (*Compt. rend.*, 1876, **82**, 512) prepared it by the new classical method of evaporating together solutions of aniline hydrochloride and ammonium thiocyanate, heating the product for some hours at 100°, washing with water and crystallising from alcohol. Clearly he thought it to be formed by the isomerisation of the aniline thiocyanate transiently produced.

The latter salt is mentioned by Dixon and Hawthorne (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **87**, 468) as a bye-product of one of their reactions; but nobody appears to have isolated it and studied its properties. Its preparation is not without difficulty. In an impure state it can be readily obtained in alcoholic solution by mixing alcoholic solutions of ammonium thiocyanate and aniline hydrochloride, filtering off the precipitated ammonium chloride and concentrating under reduced pressure in the cold. It is difficult to reduce the residual syrup to dryness without a vacuum so low that dissociative decomposition sets in; also considerable chloride remains in solution and this cannot be precipitated by ether as the required salt is itself insoluble in that solvent.

It has also been obtained by the double decomposition in concentrated aqueous solution of calcium thiocyanate and aniline hydrochloride when the required aniline thiocyanate, although itself very soluble, crystallises out in preference to the other substances present. The yield under favourable conditions is about 30% of the theory, but the conditions have to be carefully controlled or various double compounds separate (*vide* Experimental). The best method consists in the direct union of aniline and thiocyanic acid in ether when a theoretical yield is obtained.

On heating it changes with evolution of heat into phenylthiocarbamide to the extent of 80%. At 85° this is complete within 30 minutes, at 110° in 15 minutes. Attempts to follow the change were not very successful, because the heat of reaction causes the temperature to rise rapidly with consequent acceleration of the change, also because the crystallisation of solid phenylthiocarbamide (m. p. 152°) from the melt sets in fortuitously and causes a further rise of temperature, and also because the presence of this solid makes the whole so pasty that samples cannot be removed for analysis.

At all temperatures some aniline thiocyanate remains unchanged suggesting an equilibrium such as has been established between thiocarbamide and ammonium thiocyanate (Reynolds and Werner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, **83**, 1), but on heating phenylthiocarbamide for four hours at 110° no reversion occurred.

Our results agree with the fact that it is never possible to obtain more than 80% of the theoretical yield in the classical method of preparation. In verifying that this is the case we have found that potassium thiocyanate in place of the ammonium salt does not affect the yield but gives a granular, and therefore more easily handled, product of heating; we have also found that the two initial substances need only be mixed dry and heated at 110° for an hour instead of being evaporated in aqueous solution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Isolation of aniline thiocyanate.—Thiocyanic acid was prepared by passing hydrogen sulphide through a suspension of mercuric thiocyanate in ether for 3-5 hours. This was filtered and 5-10 g. of the same salt added to take up excess of hydrogen sulphide. After 12 hours this was again filtered and estimated by Volhard's method.

A measured quantity was then slowly added to one equivalent of freshly distilled aniline in ether, when a heavy liquid separated which on cooling and vigorous stirring crystallised. Sometimes it was seeded with a previously prepared sample. The product was filtered at the pump and washed 10 to 12 times with dry ether. Colourless shining scales, m.p. 80-81°, yield theoretical. It is not appreciably hygroscopic but dissolves in a quarter of its weight of water or half its weight of alcohol and insoluble in ether or benzene; its solution in water yields aniline with caustic soda solution, while titration with silver nitrate gave HSCN. (Found: S, 20.9, 21.0; HSCN, 38.7, 38.6. $C_6H_5NH_2$, HSCN requires S, 21.0; HSCN 38.8 per cent).

Interaction of aniline hydrochloride and calcium thiocyanate.—Aniline hydrochloride (65 g.) was dissolved in water (50 g.) by warming and the solution cooled to 50°; solid calcium thiocyanate (63 g.) was dissolved in this and the whole filtered. In cold weather the filtrate on standing deposited aniline thiocyanate (25 g., 30%), which was filtered off, drained at the pump and washed with ether. The mother liquor on standing for a couple of days deposited crystals of a quite different appearance which on examination proved to be a double thiocyanate of calcium and aniline. In warmer weather, however, the original solution deposited no crystals and when cooled in ice solidified to a moist mass (m. p. about 15-20°) from which no definite compound has so far been isolated. Treatment of this mass with ether resulted in a separation into three layers of which the middle one contained most of the substance. After repeated washing with ether it contained chloride, thiocyanate, aniline and calcium, probably in the equivalent-ratios of 1:3:2:2, but the total of these did not account for the total solid present; also some samples were found to undergo desulphurisation with alkaline lead solution, while complete miscibility with water precluded the presence of phenylthiocarbamide. Since the thiocyanates are well-known to have a tendency to form double compounds these observations would be of little interest but for the last which proves the presence of a substance freely soluble in water but having some of the properties of a thiocarbamide. Phenylthiocarbamide as ordinarily known is sparingly soluble in cold water (less than 1%) while aniline thiocyanate does not give the least trace of desulphurisation with alkaline lead solutions.

Evolution of heat on raising the temperature of aniline thiocyanate.—5 G. of samples were heated in baths of alcohol or toluene and a thermometer with its bulb in the melt read as follows:

TABLE I.

Time after melting.	Temp. of bath.			Time after melting.	Temp. of bath.	
	110°	85°	78°		85°	78°
2 min.	124		79	42 min.	87	82
4	122		81	48	86	91
6	118	83	82	54	86	93
12	108	86	83	60	86	85
18		87	83	66	88	79
24		87	82	72	88	
36		87	79	78	86	

It will be seen that in all cases the temperature of the melt rose above that of the bath indicating some change with evolution of heat. In a bath of 110° the maximum was attained within 2 minutes, while at lower temperatures the change was naturally less sudden.

At lower temperatures there is usually a second maximum, as can be seen above which is not uniformly reproducible and gave us a lot of trouble until we found it to be simply due to the separation of solid phenylthiocarbamide (m.p. 152°) produced in the change.

These complications seem to render hopeless any attempt to determine the velocity of the change by following it analytically as has been done in the case of ammonium thiocyanate (Atkins and Werner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 1172) where these difficulties do not seem to have been experienced.

Determination of m.p.—Since the determination of m. p. by ordinary methods cannot be relied upon owing to the occurrence of isomerisation, experiments were conducted similar to those in Table I, but paying attention to the period prior to melting. The results obtained in a bath of 86° are plotted in the diagram and it is clear that the melting point is 80° – 81° .

Heating causes isomerisation to the extent of about 80%.—A test tube containing about 5 g. was heated in a bath of boiling toluene (110°). Samples were removed after 1 and 3 hours respectively, extracted

with about 100 c.c. of cold water, the soluble portion used for the determination of thiocyanate and the insoluble residue of phenylthiocarbamide dried at 100° and weighed. The same was done at 85° . Similar experiments were performed at 70° but as at this temperature the thiocyanate takes 40 minutes to melt, during which time isomerisation is going on, the test tube was in this case first

plunged in a bath of 85° to melt the mass (6 minutes), after which it was quickly transferred to the bath at 70°. The following results are typical.

TABLE II.

Result of heating aniline thiocyanate.

Duration of heating.	Product.	Temperature of bath.		
		110°	85°	70°
1 hr.	Phenylthiocarbamide	78%	80%	64%
	Aniline thiocyanate remaining	15	12	26
	Unaccounted for	7	8	10
2 hrs.	Phenyl thiocarbamide	77	83	77
	Aniline thiocyanate remaining	12	7	15
	Unaccounted for	11	10	8

Analytical procedure presented many difficulties not all of which have been surmounted. We have hitherto failed to discover a method of estimating thiocyanic acid in the presence of phenylthiocarbamide which can be relied upon under all conditions. This will form the subject of a subsequent communication.

Nevertheless the above figures can be relied upon to within one or two units and have been repeated many times without material variation. Continued heating at the lowest temperature results in further change in the same direction, but at the higher temperatures the change is essentially complete. Indeed secondary changes are beginning to set in even after one hour at 110°. No alteration of the conditions has enabled us to obtain more than 80-83% of phenylthiocarbamide.

This suggests the attainment of an equilibrium, but such an equilibrium between aniline thiocyanate and phenylthiocarbamide is difficult to understand as our experiments were all conducted at temperatures below the melting point of phenylthiocarbamide (152°) which does not revert to aniline thiocyanate under our conditions as is shown below. The fact that 8-10% is neither aniline thiocyanate, because it does not react with silver nitrate, nor phenyl-

thiocarbamide because it is soluble in a small quantity of cold water, is probably significant. Profound decomposition is unlikely at such moderate temperatures as 70° and 85°, nor is there any sublimation, smell or colour to suggest decomposition, and one is forced to the conclusion that a third isomeric body is present, a form of phenylthiocarbamide freely soluble in cold water. If this speculation should prove to be well-founded it would clear up several difficulties.*

The change of aniline thiocyanate to phenylthiocarbamide is not reversible.—(a) 5 G. of the substance heated for 4 hours at 110° were extracted with water but thiocyanate could not be detected even qualitatively.

(b) Equal parts of the two substances were heated for 2 hours at 110°. The melt was treated exactly as before. It proved to contain phenylthiocarbamide (90%) and aniline thiocyanate (5%). Comparison of these figures with those obtained by heating the thiocyanate alone show that the latter isomerises independently of the phenylthiocarbamide introduced. If the change were an ordinary reversible one, the results would be the same in both cases.

SUMMARY.

1. Aniline thiocyanate has been isolated and examined.
2. Its isomerisation to phenylthiocarbamide, a change which has been taken for granted since 1846, has now been verified experimentally.
3. Isomerisation takes place over a wide range of temperature with considerable evolution of heat but never exceeds about 80% of the whole and some aniline thiocyanate always remains unchanged.
4. This suggests an equilibrium whereas up to 110° phenylthiocarbamide does not revert at a measurable rate.
5. This apparent equilibrium, the separation of aniline thiocyanate in liquid form during its preparation in ether, and results obtained by the interaction of aniline hydrochloride and calcium thiocyanate, indicate the existence of a third isomer hitherto unknown which undergoes desulphurisation with great ease but is freely soluble in cold water.

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* We have found that under very various conditions silver nitrate interacts with phenylthiocarbamide in the presence of nitric acid to the extent of 9-10% in excess of one equivalent.

The Phenylthiocarbamides. A Contribution to the Study of the Triad -N-C-S-. Part II. Action of Hydrolytic Agents on Phenylthiocarbamide.

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Phenylthiocarbamide may be expected to exist in one or more of the following forms: (*cf.* Werner, A new structural formula for thiocarbamide, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **101**, 2185; Krall, Constitution of guanidine, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 1398).

(I)

(II)

(III)

Hydrolysis provides an obvious line of attack on the problem of constitution, and might be expected to yield ammonia or aniline in varying proportions, with the simultaneous production of a compound having a hydroxyl group in place of the amino or anilino group. Experiments have shown, however, that this expectation is not realised, but that the hydrolytic reagent whether alkaline or acid produces decomposition of a dissociation type according to the following equations:—

In presence of a strong alkali changes (i) and (ii) occur simultaneously, but that represented by equation (i) largely predominates. With weaker alkalis changes (i) and (ii) still occur but that represented by equation (ii) increases at the expense of reaction (i). With water and weak acid, reaction (i) ceases altogether and (ii) predominates while the reaction represented by equation (iii) begins to be evident.

With strong acid changes (ii) and (iii) increase greatly (cf. the action of acetic anhydride on thiocarbanilide).

It is clear, therefore, that a progressive change in the pH value of the hydrolytic reagent causes a progressive change in the nature of the reaction and this may be due to a progressive tautomeric change in the constitution of phenylthiocarbamide. This will be discussed later.

In all cases varying but only small amounts of ammonia are produced and this is due to secondary changes such as the following :

which we have verified under the conditions of our experiments. There is no doubt that ammonia appears as a primary product only in the presence of considerable concentrations of acid when the characteristic pungent smell of mustard oil also shows itself.

In certain cases small amounts of thiocarbanilide are also produced, and this too is undoubtedly due to secondary changes.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of concentrated alkali.—Phenylthiocarbamide (7.6 g.) and caustic potash (25 g.) dissolved in water (50 c.c.) were taken in a distilling flask connected to a receiver through a condenser. The receiver was connected to a Volhard trap. Steam was passed for 3-3½ hours and the distillate which was alkaline to litmus collected. The residual solution when cold was acidified with dilute acetic acid, copious evolution of hydrogen sulphide took place and a white precipitate of phenyleyanamide settled down.

The potassium sulphide from a similar experiment was determined by titration with alkaline zinc solution. [Found: H_2S , 1.39 g., i.e., 81.7 % of theory as calculated from equation (i) above].

The alkalinity of the distillate calculated as ammonia gave $\text{NH}_3 = 0.114$ g. or 13.4 % of that calculated from equation (iii).

Evidently this change may be represented by the equation,

the ammonia being due to secondary changes as already stated.

Action of N-alkali and examination of volatile products.—Phenylthiocarbamide (7.6 g.) and caustic potash (2.8 g.) dissolved in water (50 c.c.) were treated as in previous experiment. The distillate was now acidic. It was redistilled with caustic potash and the evolved ammonia collected in standard sulphuric acid. The residual solution in the distilling flask deposited crystals of unchanged phenylthiocarbamide and was further found to contain thiocyanic acid, alkali sulphide and very small amount of phenylcyanamide. From a similar experiment the amounts of thiocyanic acid and the alkali sulphide were determined. [Found: H_2S , 0.40 g. (23.53%); HCNS , 0.089 g. (3.31%); NH_3 , 0.16 g. (18.82%).]

The estimation of thiocyanic acid in presence of hydrogen sulphide presented some difficulty. The procedure adopted was to acidify with dilute sulphuric acid, pass sulphur dioxide which within a minute or two decomposed the hydrogen sulphide in the cold; nitric acid then oxidised the excess of sulphur dioxide and the solution could be titrated with *N*/10-silver nitrate solution by Volhard's method.

Prolonged action of N-alkali.—Phenylthiocarbamide (30.4 g.) and caustic potash (11.2 g.) dissolved in water (200 c.c.) were refluxed and 5 g. samples were taken at intervals by means of a bucket formed from a length of silver wire and a small glass tube. The sample was cooled in a stoppered bottle, weighed and dissolved in water (25 c.c.), filtered from phenylthiocarbamide, etc., and the filtrate made up to 200 c.c. This procedure was rendered necessary by the fact that thiocyanic acid cannot be estimated in the presence of phenylthiocarbamide unless the quantity of the latter is small (separate communication). The amounts of hydrogen sulphide and thiocyanic acid were at once determined and their amounts in the total bulk of solution (*i.e.*, 241.6 g.) calculated. Thiocarbanilide was identified in small quantity and the smell of aniline was observed but no trace of mustard oil. The following results were obtained.

TABLE I.

Time.	Hydrogen sulphide.	Thiocyanic acid.
2 hours	19.61 %	10.14 %
4	28.04	11.64
8	20.81	22.51
13	11.71	35.99
18	8.69	44.05
22	1.31	52.0

FIG. 1.

These results in Table I and those plotted in Fig. 1 clearly indicate that the following two changes occur simultaneously :

The decline in the quantity of hydrogen sulphide after it has risen to a maximum remains unexplained.

Effect of varying amounts of caustic potash and of water alone.—Phenylthiocarbamide (5 g.) was refluxed with 1, $\frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{1}{4}$, $\frac{1}{8}$, $\frac{1}{16}$, 0 equivalent of caustic potash respectively dissolved in 132 c.c. of water, for 1 hour. The amounts of hydrogen sulphide and thiocyanic acid were estimated as before with the following results.

TABLE II.

Caustic potash.	Hydrogen sulphide.	Thiocyanic acid.
1 equiv.	23.20 %	5.7 %
1/2	8.67	6.8
1/4	2.29	7.0
1/8	0.86	7.9
1/16	Traces	8.7
0	Absent	8.81

This experiment shows that diminishing alkalinity favours the second change.

Action of barium hydroxide solution.—Phenylthiocarbamide (5 g.) was refluxed with 1 equivalent of barium hydroxide dissolved in 33 c.c. of water for an hour. The results obtained with one equivalent of caustic potash under identical conditions are given for comparison.

TABLE III.

Alkali.	Hydrogen sulphide.	Thiocyanic acid.
Barium hydroxide.	13.24 %	9.89 %
Caustic potash.	29.6	6.06

This experiment shows that a weaker alkali has the same effect as a more dilute alkali, *i. e.*, that the effects observed are due to the p_H values.

Action of acids.—Phenylthiocarbamide (5 g.) was heated under reflux with one equivalent of acid diluted with 50 c.c. of water for an hour. No trace of hydrogen sulphide was evolved. The percentage of thiocyanic acid was estimated. The results obtained are summed up in the following table.

TABLE IV.

Acid.	Hydrogen sulphide.	Thiocyanic acid.	Mustard oil.
Acetic	Nil	16.08 %	Faint smell.
Hydrochloric	Nil	61.85	Strong smell

SUMMARY.

1. Phenylthiocarbamide does not suffer hydrolysis of the normal type.
2. Hydrolytic agents produce decompositions of a dissociation type represented by the following equations:

3. Change No. (i) takes place only under alkaline conditions; (ii) occurs over a wide range but is favoured by increasing acidity; (iii) becomes appreciable only in the presence of strong acid.

4. In other words the carbon-sulphur bond is the first to be ruptured in the presence of alkali, the carbon-anilino in the presence of acids, the carbon-amine in the presence of the strongest acids.

Discussion of the bearing of these results on the problem of constitution is postponed pending the completion of further investigations now in progress.

Some of the above experiments were performed by Mr. G. V. Halwe, M.Sc.